

Potentiometric Studies on the Systems Zn(II)/Cd(II)-Nitrilotriacetic acid-Dicarboxylic acids.

KIRAN KAPOOR, VINOD KUMARI, R. C. SHARMA and G. K. CHATURVEDI

Chemical Laboratories, Agra College, Agra

Manuscript received 19 November 1976 ; accepted 21 March 1977

Formation of 1 : 1 : 1 ternary complexes in the system : Zn(II)/Cd(II)-NTA-H₂A (where H₂A = oxalic (OX), malonic (MALN), succinic (SUC), phthalic acid (PHA)) has been evidenced potentiometrically. The formation constants and thermodynamic functions viz. ΔG , ΔH and ΔS have been calculated for the resulting complexes at $25 \pm 1^\circ$ and $35 \pm 1^\circ$. The order of stability in terms of metal is Zn(II) > Cd(II).

A survey of the literature revealed that the formation of mixed ligand complexes M(II)-X-Y (where M(II) = Zn(II), Cd(II) ; X = diamines, heterocyclic bases and Y = mono or dicarboxylic acids and their substituted derivatives) have been reported¹⁻⁵. Tandón and coworkers⁶ have carried out potentiometric studies on the ternary systems Zn(II)-NTA-hydroxy acids. However, no work appears to have been done on the systems Zn(II)/Cd(II)-NTA-dicarboxylic acids. Therefore, it has been considered worthwhile to undertake potentiometric studies on some of these systems with a view to determine the formation constants and the thermodynamic functions i.e. free energies of formation (ΔG), enthalpy (ΔH) and entropy (ΔS) changes for the resulting species.

Materials : All the chemicals used were of Analar BDH grade. Stock solutions of zinc nitrate and cadmium nitrate were prepared by dissolving zinc oxide and cadmium carbonate in nitric acid. The solutions were standardised gravimetrically for Zn(II) and Cd(II) as zinc ammonium phosphate and cadmium anthranilate respectively.

Standard solution of dicarboxylic acids H₂A : oxalic acid (OX), malonic (MALN), succinic (SUC) and phthalic acid (PHA) were prepared by direct weighing. NTA was used as its disodium salt. The concentrations of all the ligands were checked by pH titrations.

Instruments : The pH measurements were recorded with a Precision Philips pH meter (PR 9405 M) at $25 \pm 1^\circ$ and $35 \pm 1^\circ$ (maintained in a thermostat). The instrument was standardised with 0.05 M potassium hydrogen phthalate (pH=4). Ionic strength ($\mu=0.1M$ KNO₃), total volume (50 ml) and the concentration ($5 \times 10^{-3} M$ in terms of metal and the ligands) were kept constant at the beginning of the titration.

Calculations : The pK values of oxalic, malonic, phthalic acids and NTA were calculated by the method of Chaberek and Martell⁷ and that of succinic acid by

the Noyes method⁸. The calculated values determined at $25 \pm 1^\circ$ and $35 \pm 1^\circ$ for dicarboxylic acids H₂A, (OX - pK₁=1.65, pK₂=4.14 ; MALN - pK₁=2.95, pK₂=5.82 ; SUC - pK₁=4.19, pK₂=5.49 ; PHA - pK₁=3.39, pK₂=5.46) are in accordance with Segeant⁹ whereas pK₁ of NTA at the respective temperatures are found to be 9.82 and 10.05.

Formation constants (K_{MLL}) of the ternary complexes formed by the simultaneous addition of the two ligands were calculated by the method of Ramamoorthy and Santappa¹⁰.

The free energies of formation (ΔG), enthalpy (ΔH) and entropy (ΔS) changes at $25 \pm 1^\circ$ and $35 \pm 1^\circ$ were calculated by the following expressions :

$$\Delta G = -RT \ln K_{MLL}$$

$$\Delta H = \frac{2.303 RT_1 T_2 (\log \beta_2 - \log \beta_1)}{T_2 - T_1}$$

$$\Delta S = \frac{\Delta H - \Delta G}{T}$$

where R is the gas constant,

T₁ and T₂ are the temperatures in absolute degrees β_1 and β_2 are the formation constants at T₁ and T₂ respectively,

The values of ΔG , ΔH and ΔS are given in table 1.

Results and Discussion

System M(II)-NTA

On titrating the solution containing equimolar ratio of Zn(II) or Cd(II) and NTA, a sharp inflection at $m=1$ (where m =moles of base added per mole of ligand) in curve a and a' for Zn(II) and Cd(II) respectively in

TABLE I

System	log $K_{MLL'}$		ΔG (Kcal/mole)		ΔH	ΔS (cal/mole/degree)	
	25±1°C	35±1°C	25+1°C	35+1°C	(Kcal/mole)	25+1°C	35+1°C
Zn(II)-NTA-OX	7.88±0.16	7.69±0.13	-10.740	-10.835	-7.980	+ 9.261	+ 9.269
Cd(II)-NTA-OX	7.21±0.14	7.02±0.13	- 9.827	- 9.891	-7.980	+ 6.198	+ 6.204
Zn(II)-NTA-MALN	12.20±0.19	12.02±0.20	-16.628	-16.936	-7.560	+30.429	+30.441
Cd(II)-NTA-MALN	11.16±0.21	11.04±0.23	-15.279	-15.555	-7.140	+27.312	+27.321
Zn(II)-NTA-SUC	12.93±0.30	12.75±0.34	-17.623	-17.964	-7.560	+33.769	+33.779
Cd(II)-NTA-SUC	12.13±0.34	11.90±0.33	-16.532	-16.767	-9.660	+23.063	+23.074
Zn(II)-NTA-PHA	12.03±0.18	11.86±0.24	-16.396	-16.710	-7.140	+31.060	+31.071
Cd(II)-NTA-PHA	11.16±0.23	10.97±0.26	-15.211	-15.456	-7.980	+24.265	+24.272

Fig. I, indicates the formation of 1 : 1 binary M(II)-NTA complex as depicted below :

$M(II) - H_2A$

The curves b and b' in Figs. I—IV for the binary systems involving Zn(II), Cd(II) respectively, in the presence of equimolar amount of H_2A , exhibit inflections at $m=2$ due to the formation of 1 : 1 $M(II) - H_2A$ binary complex. Another inflection at $m \approx 4$ may be attributed to the disproportionation of the initially formed binary species giving more stable 1 : 2 complex with the precipitation of a part of the metal as hydrated

metal oxide

$System M(II) - NTA - H_2A$

Curves c and c' in Figs. I—IV represent the ternary systems involving 1 : 1 : 1 Zn(II)/Cd(II)-NTA- H_2A . A single sharp inflection at $m=3$ may be correlated to the formation of 1 : 1 : 1 ternary complex by the simultaneous addition of two ligands to the metal ion. The formation of ternary species is further supported by the non-appearance of a solid phase during the

Fig. I

Fig. II

Fig. I curve a = Zn(II)-NTA, a' = Cd(II)-NTA; b = Zn(II)-OX, b' = Cd(II)-OX; c = Zn(II)-NTA-OX, c' = Cd(II)-NTA-OX

Fig. II curve b = Zn(II)-MALN, b' = Cd(II)-MALN; c = Zn(II)-NTA-MALN, c' = Cd(II)-NTA-MALN.

Fig. III

Fig. IV

Fig. III curve b = Zn(II)-SUC, b' = Cd(II)-SUC; c = Zn(II)-NTA-SUC, c' = Cd(II)-NTA-SUC.

Fig. IV curve b = Zn(II)-PHA, b' = Cd(II)-PHA; c = Zn(II)-NTA-PHA, c' = Cd(II)-NTA-PHA

titration :

(where $H_2A=OX, MALN, SUC$ or PHA).

A comparison of the values of formation constants of the ternary species show the order of stability in terms of metal as $Zn(II) > Cd(II)$ in accordance with the Williams Irving^{1,2} series whereas in terms of dicarboxylic acids the order of stability is $OX < MALN \approx SUC \approx PHA$ which may be attributed to the increasing basicities : $OX < MALN \approx SUC \approx PHA$ probably caused by the increasing inductive influence of CH_2 groups in the ligand molecules. Increasing size of the dicarboxylic acid ions (A^{2-}) show a progressive increase to the extent to which polarization of the (A^{2-}) by metal ion is caused. Larger the magnitude of polarization, stronger is the covalent bond formed. The other factor such as presence of as many as three, five-membered rings resulting from the chelation of the metal-ion with NTA may also play an important role and cannot be set-aside while discussing the stabilities of the above ternary species.

The values of ΔG and ΔS (table 1) correspond to the formation constants of the respective ternary species. The increasing positive values of ΔS , give more negative values of ΔG . More the negative value of ΔG , stronger is the complex formed.

Acknowledgement

The authors express their deep sense of gratitude to Dr. J. P. Tandon, Reader in Chemistry, Rajasthan University, Jaipur for his valuable suggestions. They also thank Agra College authorities for providing the laboratory facilities.

References

1. V. KANEMURA and J. J. WATTERS, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1967, 29(7), 1701.
2. N. F. CURTIS, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1968, A(7), 1584.
3. GRIESSER ROLF, PRIJS BERNHARD and SIGEL HELMUT, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1968, 4(8), 443.
4. GRIESSER ROLF, PRIJS BERNHARD, SIGEL HELMUT, MC CORMIC and B. DONALD, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1969, 5(12), 951.
5. B. V. TRONOV and R. T. KHARITANOVA TRUDY, *Inst. Khim. Akad. Nauk. Kirgis. S.S.R.*, 1955, No. 6, 157.
6. G. SHARMA and J. P. TANDON, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1970, 32(4), 1273.
7. S. CHABEREK JR. and A. E. MARTELL, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1952, 74, 5052.
8. A. A. NOYES, *Z. Physik. Chem.*, 1893, 11, 495.
9. A. ALBERT and E. P. SERGEANT, "The determination of ionization constants" (Chapman & Hall, London) 1971, p. 7.
10. S. RAMAMOORTHY and SANTAPPA, *Ind. J. Chem.*, 1971, 9(4), 381.
11. H. IRVING and R. J. P. WILLIAMS, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, 75, 3192.